

Annual Generation

BAU

90% Renewable Energies

100% Renewable Energies

- Geothermal
- Natural Gas (CCGT)
- Natural Gas (SCGT)
- Oil
- Solar PV
- Large Hydro
- Medium Hydro
- Wind
- Utility-scale PV
- Solar (Distributed)
- Off-grid Hydro
- Biomass

Total Capacity

BAU

90% Renewable Energies

100% Renewable Energies

- Geothermal
- Natural Gas (CCGT)
- Natural Gas (SCGT)
- Oil
- Solar PV
- Large Hydro
- Medium Hydro
- Wind
- Utility-scale PV
- Solar (Distributed)
- Off-grid Hydro
- Biomass

Capital Investment

BAU

100% Renewable Energies

- Biomass
- Solar Distributed
- Utility-scale PV
- Medium Hydro
- Large Hydro
- Solar PV
- Oil
- Natural Gas (SCGT)
- Geothermal

Annual Emissions

